

MODERN METHODS OF TEETH HYPERSENSITIVITY TREATMENT IN DIFFERENT GROUPS OF INDIVIDUALS

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Resume.

Hypersensitivity of the teeth is one of the most common complaint of patients, which, as a rule, leads them to the dentist. Most often, hypersensitivity manifests itself as a sharp or moderate pain when exposed to various factors, these can be chemical (sour food), thermal (most often it is cold water, ice cream, a sharp change in cold drinks or food to warm) and mechanical (toothbrush, toothpick).

Hypersensitivity of hard tissues of the teeth, occurs quite often in violation of the structure of teeth's hard tissues (caries process, increased abrasion of dental tissues, enamel erosion, wedge-shaped defects, etc.), periodontal diseases, and in some cases without visible changes in teeth .

Key words: *hypersensitivity of dental hard tissues, remineralizing therapy, Denta-Fluo.*

The relevance of this article lies in the fact that ,in the group of elderly patients (55-75 year-olds) there were used various methods of treating this disease, each of which has its own advantages and disadvantages.

The article aims to compare several methods of hypersensitivity treatment of dental hard tissues and their effectiveness. Hypersensitivity of teeth is one of the most common complaints of patients, which, as a rule, lead them to the dentist. Most often, hypersensitivity manifests itself as a sharp or moderate soreness when exposed to various factors, these can be chemical (sour food), thermal (most often it is cold water, ice cream, a sharp change from cold drinks or food to warm) and mechanical (toothbrush, toothpick). Hypersensitivity of dental hard tissues, occurs

quite often in violation of the dental hard tissues' structure (caries process, increased abrasion of dental tissues, enamel erosion, wedge-shaped defects, etc.), periodontal diseases, and also in some cases without visible changes in teeth .

Purpose of the study: To evaluate the effectiveness of the treatment of hypersensitivity of dental hard tissues using various methods.

Materials and methods of examination: 24 people aged 55–75 years with hypersensitivity of dental hard tissues were under observation. All patients were taught hygienic care of the oral cavity and were divided into 2 groups: 1st (controlling group) - 12 individuals received local remineralizing therapy according to the method of P. A. Leus, E. V. Borovsky (applications of 10% calcium gluconate solution) , within 20 days. In the 2nd group (experimental group) — 12 patients received treatment fluorine-containing preparation from the company Dentals Pharma GmbH - "Denta-Fluo". Hypersensitivity of teeth hard tissues was detected by taking an anamnesis and complaints of patients to various irritants. During the collection of anamnesis, it was revealed that 30% of the individuals complained of thermal stimuli, 20% of chemical stimuli, and 50% had complaints of common irritants. Remineralizing therapy is a local prevention of dental caries, by restoring the mineral composition of teeth, helps to maintain the resistance of the enamel to the caries process and eliminate the increased sensitivity of teeth. E. V. Borovsky and P. A. Leus (1972) proposed a method for the prevention and treatment of initial manifestations of dental caries by using calcium gluconate and sodium fluoride. Before a prophylaxis session, patients brush their teeth for 2-3 minutes of hygienic paste. Next, the teeth are lined with cotton swabs moistened with a 10% solution of calcium gluconate. The application lasts 3-5 minutes. Upon completion of the application of gluconate, the second stage of the procedure is carried out: the teeth are covered with rollers moistened with a 2% solution of sodium fluoride for 1–2 minutes. Treatment with "Denta-Fluo" is a new and very effective component of the treatment of hypersensitivity of dental hard tissues .This preparation contains a special varnish containing in equal amounts of sodium fluoride and calcium

fluoride, which provides a quick and lasting result. The good effect is explained first by the sealing of the dentinal tubules with varnish and the rapid elimination of pain, and then by the gradual stimulation of the formation of secondary dentin by calcium fluoride compounds. Stages of treatment of dental hypersensitivity by using the drug "Denta-Fluo", the first step is to preliminarily clean the teeth with a professional fluoride-free paste, isolation of teeth from saliva using standard rollers.

The surface of teeth, previously dried with warm air, was treated with Denta-Fluo using sponge balls (Pele Tim). After application, the varnish was left on the tooth surface for 20 seconds. The patient was not recommended to eat solid food for two hours and not to brush his teeth for 12 hours after the procedure.

Clinical observations show that with such a complex treatment of hypersensitivity of dental hard tissues, the effect occurs rather quickly and is persistent, since remineralization processes occur both from the side of the enamel and from the side of the pulp: the content of calcium phosphate in the tissues of the tooth increases.

Results. In the treatment of hypersensitivity of dental hard tissues by various methods, we obtained the following results. When using the method of "remineralizing therapy" by a conservative method, complaints decreased in seven of those surveyed, in five they completely disappeared. During the treatment with the drug "Denta-Fluo" in the control group, all the complaints completely disappeared in all of the participants of poll sample.

With the traditional method, the course of treatment was 10 sessions and each individual procedure (including preparation to the procedure) took about (20-25 minutes), which, according to the patients, seemed very inconvenient, and when treated with Denta-Fluo, patients expressed positive opinions, apparently the reason for this, was not only the complete absence of pain reaction to various stimuli, but also the duration of treatment (in one visit).

Conclusions: Summing up, as a result of our study, we found that the treatment of hypersensitivity of dental hard tissues by using the drug "Denta-Fluo" is more effective and takes less time.

Bibliography:

1. Patrikeev, B.K. Diseases of teeth of non-carious origin / V.K. Patrikeev // Therapeutic dentistry textbook. - M.: Medicine, 1982.-S.136-140.
2. Borovsky, E.V. Non-carious lesions of the teeth: clinic and treatment / E.V. Borovsky, P.A. Leus, G.K. Lebedeva. - M.: Medicine, 1978. - 16 p.
3. Garage, I.S. Treatment of pathological abrasion of teeth using hydroxyapatite and fluorine-containing drugs: Abstract of the thesis. dis. ... cand. honey. Sciences / I.S. Garazh. - Stavropol, 2004. - 22 p.
4. V.A. Osipova, P.A. Burdina /Comparative analysis of the effectiveness of the use of dental preparations to reduce hypersensitivity of teeth// SCIENTIFIC NOTES SPbGMU im. acad. I. P. Pavlova - S.57-62
5. A. K. Iordanishvili, A. K. Orlov, V. V. Yankovsky / Hypersensitivity of dental hard tissues: prevalence and age-related features of the clinical course in elderly and senile people // Bulletin of St. Petersburg University 2014 - issue 4 - pp 137-144
6. Kovalenko I.P. /Efficiency of treatment of hyperesthesia of hard tissues of teeth by remineralization method /Belarusian Medical Academy of Postgraduate Education, Minsk// MODERN DENTISTRY N2 2013 P.85-88
7. Ivanova, T.I. Refinement of the crystal structure of apatite enamel of human teeth of the older age group / T.I. Ivanova, V.V. Golubtsov, O.V. Frank-Kamenetskaya, A.N. Shmakov // Mineralogical Museums. - St. Petersburg: St. Petersburg State University. - 2005. - P.246.
8. S.I. Gazhva, N.N.Shurova, O.V. doi.org/10.17116/stomat20189705111
9. Kamilov Kh.P. Saidova N.A. Experimental methods for reproducing gingivitis // Actual problems of fundamental, clinical medicine and the possibility

of distance learning. Materials of the international scientific and practical online conference. Samarkand, 2020. - P. 58.

10. Saidova N.A. The use of vector therapy for the treatment of hypertrophic gingivitis in adolescents // 1st Scientific and Practical Conference with International Participation. Topical issues of dentistry. - Moscow, 2018.

11. Kamilov Kh.P., Saidova N.A., Takhirova K.A., Makhmudova N.Z. Changes in indicators of local immunity of the gums and oral cavity in the treatment of hypertrophic gingivitis in adolescents // A new day in medicine. - Bukhara, 2020. - No. 2 (30). - S. 382-386.

12. Saidova N.A., Zoyirov T.E. Features of hypertrophic gingivitis in adolescents // Uzbekistan medical journals. - Tashkent, 2019. No. 3. S.83-85.